

Supplementary Figure 1- Results of using an edge-based approach for inferring relationships of simulated levels of incomplete lineage sorting. The filled in circles represent the total number of edges that were inferred for the Edge Consensus Tree, in the case of the Bifurcating Tree and Supermatrix tree, no polytomies are inferred and therefore eight edges are always inferred. The open circles are the number of edges that are inferred and conflict with the simulated topology.

Supplementary Figure 2. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 10 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 3. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 10 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology and only well supported branches ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) included. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 4. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 10 taxa with 90 genes simulated on one topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 5. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 10 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology, 10 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported branches ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) included. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and are well supported.

Supplementary Figure 6. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 10 taxa with 50 genes simulated on one topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 7. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 10 taxa with 50 genes simulated under one topology and 50 genes under random topologies and only the edges that have at least 95% UFboot support are analyzed. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 8. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 50 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 9. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 50 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 10. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 50 taxa with 90 genes simulated on one topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 11. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 50 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 12. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 50 taxa with 50 genes simulated on one topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 13. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 50 taxa with 50 genes simulated on a single topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < UFboot$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 14. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 100 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 15. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 100 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 16. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 100 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 17. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 100 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 18. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 100 taxa with 50 genes simulated on a single topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 19. Simulated nucleotide datasets for 100 taxa with 50 genes simulated on a single topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 20. Simulated amino acid datasets for 10 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 21. Simulated amino datasets for 10 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology and only well supported branches ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) included. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 22. Simulated amino acid datasets for 10 taxa with 90 genes simulated on one topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 23. Simulated amino acid datasets for 10 taxa with 10% of the genes in conflict and only the edges that have at least 95% UFboot support are analyzed. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 24. Simulated amino acid datasets for 10 taxa with 50 genes simulated on one topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 25. Simulated amino acid datasets for 10 taxa with 50 genes simulated under one topology and 50 genes under random topologies and only the edges that have at least 95% UFboot support are analyzed. Each boxplot considers the seventeen branches that are found in a ten taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and are well supported.

Supplementary Figure 26. Simulated amino acid datasets for 50 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 27. Simulated amino acid datasets for 50 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 28. Simulated amino acid datasets for 50 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology, 10 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 29. Simulated amino acid datasets for 50 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 30. Simulated amino datasets for 50 taxa with 50 genes simulated on one topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 31. Simulated amino acid datasets for 50 taxa with 50 genes simulated on a single topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < UFboot$) analyzed. This is an enlarged version of the data presented in the main figure 5. Each boxplot considers the ninety-seven branches that are found in a fifty taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 32. Simulated amino acid datasets for 100 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 33. Simulated amino acid datasets for 100 taxa with 100 genes simulated on a single topology and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 34. Simulated amino acid datasets for 100 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 35. Simulated amino acid datasets for 100 taxa with 90 genes simulated on a single topology and 10 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.

Supplementary Figure 36. Simulated amino acid datasets for 100 taxa with 50 genes simulated on a single topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant.

Supplementary Figure 37. Simulated amino acid datasets for 100 taxa with 50 genes simulated on a single topology and 50 genes simulated on random topologies and only well supported ($95 < \text{UFboot}$) analyzed. Each boxplot considers the one-hundred and ninety-seven branches that are found in a 100 taxa tree which are ordered from smallest value to largest value. The x-axis in all panels is the molecular rate of the branch on a simulated tree presented to two significant digits for clarity. Blue, red and orange represent boxplots of 100 replicates for the supermatrix, mean, and median methods of inference respectively with the y-axis being the absolute value of the distance between the simulated rate and the rate inferred using each method. In black are boxplots for 100 replicates examining the total number of branches that are concordant and well supported.